

Bank Operations, Insecurity and Agricultural Sector Productivity in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined bank operation, insecurity and agricultural sector productivity in Nigeria. Lending rate (LR), deposit rate (DR), kidnaping rate (KPR), and armed robbery rate (ARR), were the independent variables while agricultural sector contribution to gross domestic product (AGDP), was used to proxy the agricultural sector productivity as a dependent variable. Secondary data was used for the analysis which covered a period of 37 years (1985 to 2022). For the purpose of ensuring stationarity and conducting an analysis of the data, the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF), the Auto-Regressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) bound test, and the error correction model were used. With regard to the short-run, it was discovered that LR had a negative but substantial link with AGDP in the prior and second year period. On the other hand, KPR likewise indicated a negative but significant relationship with AGDP in the long-run. DR, have a positive but negligible association with AGDP in the near term. Last but not least, the analysis of the link between ARR and AGDP indicated that it is both negative and negligible in the long run, as well as in the second year period of the short run. Also, the coefficient of the ECM suggests that the rate of adjustment to long run equilibrium is 0.03% when any departure from the past is rectified in the current period. As a result, the conclusion that was reached was that the functioning of banks and the level of security in Nigeria had a substantial influence on the productivity of the agricultural sector. It was recommended amongst others that monetary policy authority (CBN), should immediately reduce the rising lending rate as a target variable to control inflation, expand farmer's access to credit which will enhance productivity and job creation.

Keywords: Lending Rate, Deposit Rate, Kidnaping Rate, Armed Robbery Rate, Agricultural Sector Productivity.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years the nexus between financial institutions, security challenges, and the productivity of agricultural sector has emerged as a critical area of concern for policymakers, economists, and researchers. This research delves into the intricate relationship among these factors, specifically exploring the impact of bank operations and insecurity on the productivity trajectory of the agricultural sector. As the backbone of many economies, the agricultural sector plays a

pivotal role in ensuring food security and sustainable development. The agricultural sector is a significant instrument for the growth of a country since it not only assures a steady supply of food and safety for the people, but it also ensures that the workforce is nourished with energy so that it can provide labour to companies. The agricultural value added per worker is expected to considerably rise as nations develop, mostly as a result of advances in productivity, knowledge, and efficiency. This is a direct consequence of growth in agricultural production. According to Mouayadi et al. (2020), agriculture may be viewed in a straightforward manner as the process of generating food, feed, fibre, and any other desired goods via the cultivation of plants and the breeding of domesticated animals. This understanding encompasses both the practice of agriculture and the research that is conducted on agriculture. As a tool for development, the agricultural subsector contributes to the reduction of poverty by encouraging farmers and their families to engage in subsistence farming as well as commercial farming, which together will enhance their quality of living and guarantee that they have access to food.

Consequently, the agricultural sector is the main stay of the economies of less developed nations (such as Ghana, Niger, Malawi, Gambia, and Nigeria, among others), serving as the foundation for their food security, revenues from exports, and rural development. With the right policies, the agricultural sector is capable of reducing poverty, raise income and improve standard of living of the people. Financial institutions like banks are crucial financial intermediaries intricately tied to economic activities, and disruptions in their operations can reverberate across various sector. Bank operations refers to the day to day activities and functions conducted by a bank to provide financial services to its customers and manage its own resources. These operations encompass a wide range of activities that are essential for the functioning of a bank. These areas includes; deposit and withdrawal, loans and credit, payment and transactions, foreign exchange operations investment, risk management and customer service etc. According to Olokoyo et al (2016) bank operations means operating different accounts (current, savings & fixed deposit) receiving deposits, paying out notes and coins and giving loans. In line with this view, Ireokwu and Ukanwata (2022), sees bank operation as not only to facilitate economic growth, but to speed-up the process of economic growth through making funds available from resources mobilized, encourage investments, provide direct loans to government and individuals for investment purposes. Through this process, banks contribute to the agricultural sector.

Concurrently, the rise in security, both in traditional and emerging forms, poses a multifaceted challenge to economic stability. Insecurity encompasses a range of threats to individuals, communities and nations. These include but not limited to crime, conflict, economic instability, and vulnerabilities to external pressures. According to Okonkwo et al. (2015), the term “insecurity” describes a condition of vulnerability that may result in threats to one’s life, property, and means of subsistence. A condition of anxiety that arises from the absence of protection from an assault or threat, or from a lack of freedom from danger, is thus referred to as insecure. It is important to note that insecurity is a menace to growth of the economy. Therefore, understanding and addressing it, is paramount as it not only impacts the safety and livelihoods of individuals but also influences economic development, social cohesion, and the overall stability of regions and nations.

However, it is relevant to note that agricultural sector productivity is strongly reliant on bank operation and security situation (Insecurity) of a country. For instance, effective bank operations that provide accessible and affordable financial services to farmers can enhance agricultural productivity through loans for purchasing seeds, fertilizes and modern equipment, as well as

working capital. More so, bank operations especially those focused on infrastructure financing, can contribute to the development of rural infrastructure (e.g. irrigation, transportation). Improved infrastructure enhances agricultural productivity by facilitating the movement of goods and reducing post-harvest losses. In line with this view, Ijeomah and Wonah (2022) in their study indicated that the decrease in food production by peasant farmers is the cause of the rise in the cost of food items in the state of Delta. Because of the numerous assaults by herders, which resulted in the loss of crops and violent attacks that resulted in the deaths of over 194 people, many of these peasant farmers have lost interest in farming. This is the outcome of the frequent attacks committed by herdsmen.

Also, through risk management function, bank, design financial productions that considers and mitigates risks, providing stability to farmers in regions prone to insecurity. This is achieved by investing heavily on cyber security to safeguard their system and data from hacking, malware, phishing attacks and other cyber threats. However, in recent times insecurity impacts banks willingness to operate in certain regions or lend to agricultural enterprises, thereby limiting farmer's access to crucial financial resources. Furthermore, insecurity introduces uncertainties and risks that can affect the financial health of banks. Heightened risks may lead to more conservative lending practices which reduces the availability of credit for agriculture. Conclusively, insecurity can hinder infrastructural development as it may deter investment and disrupt construction projects, limiting the positive impact of bank operations on agricultural productivity.

Despite the high level of insecurity and lending rate, statistical data in the past revealed that in 2017 the contribution of agricultural sector to the gross domestic product stood at ₦23952.51 billion and rose to ₦27371.30 billion in 2018. The value of agricultural sector contribution to gross domestic product further increase to ₦31904.14 billion, ₦37241.61 billion and ₦41126.06 billion between 2019, 2020 and 2021 (CBN, 2021). However, as a chief sector of the Nigeria economy, further statistical information showed that the agricultural sector has not performed well when compared to other sectors such as the industrial and service sector. This is probably due to insecurity and high interest rate. For instance, industrial sector contribution to gross domestic product stood at ₦25639.90 billion in 2019 and ₦33218.33 billion in 2018. The value of industrial sector increased to ₦39879.69 billion, ₦43530.78 billion and ₦55300.97 billion between 2019, 2020 and 2021. Correspondingly, within the period service sector reported ₦64119.18 billion in 2017 and ₦67147.20 billion in 2018. Subsequent years like 2019, 2020 and 2021 reported ₦72426.66 billion, ₦71551.68 billion and ₦77100.63 billion respectively. Therefore, this paper seeks to answer the following questions; how has lending rate enhanced agricultural sector productivity? Has deposit rate contributed to agricultural sector productivity? Has kidnaping rate affected agricultural sector productivity? And has armed robbery rate affected agricultural sector productivity? To answer these questions, this research made a contribution to the existing body of knowledge by conducting an empirical investigation into the impact of bank operations and insecurity on agricultural sector production in Nigeria from 1985 to 2021. As a result, the scope of the study was expanded in comparison to what had been done in the past. According to the following format, the remainder of the work is organized as follows: after this introduction in section 1, section 2 handles theoretical and empirical literature. The techniques of the study, including the definitions of the variables used in the research, are discussed in section 3, while the findings are presented in section 4. section 5 concludes the work.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature

2.1.1 Democratic Peace Theory

Doyle (1998) proposed the Democratic Peace hypothesis as a possible political philosophy. According to this idea, the primary factor in determining the level of security is the degree to which liberal institutions are encouraged to fulfil their commitments and responsibilities in a credible manner. It went on to argue that the policy of security ought to be liberalized over the course of a lengthy period of time. All of this is taking place against the backdrop of the fact that the path to peace is to enthrone and foster democratic systems, broad respect for human rights, and the promotion of the growth of civil society. On the other hand, this is contingent upon the existence of a stable and unshakeable connection between the democratic norm of a country and its tendency towards peacefulness. Therefore, the democratic peace theory holds the belief that states that are tolerant do not engage in war against other nations. According to Doyle, there was a tolerance for divergence in liberal cultures, and vice versa to conservative civilizations. It is also implied that if liberal institutions (law enforcement agencies) such as the police, army, navy, and so on are able to fulfil their obligations in a credible manner, there would be a reduction in crime or insecurity, which will open the way for the efficient and quick expansion of various sectors of the economy.

2.1.2 Commercial Loan Theory

The commercial loan idea, often known as the Real Bills Doctrine, was proposed by Lloyd Mints in the year 1945. In accordance with this theory, a commercial bank should only provide short-term self-liquidating productive loans to business firms. Self-liquidating loans are loans that are intended to finance the production of goods as well as the movement of those goods through the various stages of production, including storage, transportation, and distribution. According to Jhingan (2009), the debts are judged to have automatically liquidated themselves when the particular products in question are eventually sold. According to Mbat (2001), when a bank provides financing for a company's working capital, the bank anticipates that the bank will get money for repayment from the management of the working capital itself. The central bank should only lend money to commercial banks based on the security of short-term loans, according to the theory, which proposes that when commercial banks only issue loans for short-term liquidation productive purposes, the central bank should lend money to the banks. Taking into consideration this theory in relation to the agricultural industry, it is anticipated that commercial banks would provide farmers with short-term loans that include self-liquidating provisions in order to meet their need for working capital. It is anticipated that the loans would be used mostly for agricultural endeavors, and the repayment of the loans should be determined by the profits generated by the farm.

2.1.3 Neoclassical theory of Production

Ferguson postulated the Neo-classical theory of production in 2008. The theory states that the rate of interest is established by the demand and supply of capital, or by the intersection of the investment demand schedule and the supply/saving schedule. On the other hand, the neo-classical theory of production emphasizes that in order to achieve the optimal level of production, resources must be available and efficiently utilized. As a result of the fact that loans extended to farmers are intended to be repaid, this is closely connected to the objective of the Deposit Money Banks and the production of agricultural goods. However, it would be difficult for the Deposit Money Banks to recover such loans unless they first make the money

accessible to the farmers and make certain that these resources are used in an effective manner in order to achieve the highest potential level of output. Moreover, the welfare of farmers can be improved as a result of the efficient utilization of resources; consequently, the specification of the neoclassical theory of production can be utilized to accomplish the mission of the Deposit Money Banks, which is to generate profits from the improved welfare of farmers in the area under study.

2.2 Review of Related Empirical Studies

Numerous empirical studies have been carried out in the field of the relationship between bank operation, insecurity and agricultural sector productivity. In several instances, however, the outcomes of such studies were contradictory and inconsistent with one another. An example of this would be the research conducted by Akinuli and Osagiede (2023), who investigated the impact that agricultural funding from deposit money banks and the government had on agricultural production in Nigeria. The statistics bulletin published by the Central Bank of Nigeria was the source of the time series data that was utilised, which covered the years 1983 through 2022. According to the findings of the research, the actions of banks and the government in terms of financing agriculture have a beneficial impact on the amounts of agricultural products produced throughout the time period under review. Furthermore, Mbotto et al. (2022) investigated the influence that bank lending had on the growth of the agricultural sector in Nigeria by using time series data spanning from 1990 to 2020. There was a negative and significant relationship between commercial bank credit to the agricultural sector and agricultural output index in Nigeria. On the other hand, the study revealed that there was a positive and significant relationship between agricultural credit guarantee scheme loan and agricultural production output index. Once again, the distribution of government funding had a large and detrimental impact on the agricultural output index. In addition, there was a large and favourable correlation between the price of agricultural output and the index of agricultural productivity.

Ijeomah and Wonah (2022) conducted a research on the link between food insecurity and the food production of peasant farmers in the state of Delta in Nigeria. The data from secondary sources were presented in tables and descriptive analysis was performed on the data. The findings indicated that the decrease in food production by peasant farmers is the cause of the rise in the cost of food items in the state of Delta. Because of the numerous assaults by herders, which resulted in the loss of crops and violent attacks that resulted in the deaths of over 194 people, many of these peasant farmers have lost interest in farming. This is the outcome of the frequent attacks committed by herdsmen. A similar study was conducted by Onuegbu et al. (2022) to investigate the impact that commercial bank lending has on agricultural production in Nigeria. According to the findings of the research, the impact of bank credit on agricultural production, government investment on the agricultural sector, and the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund all have a positive and substantial impact on agricultural output. On the other hand, the impact of interest rate on agricultural output is negative and minor. In addition, Ilesanmi and Odefadehan (2022) investigated the influence of insecurity on agricultural food loss in Nigeria by using time series data spanning the years 2011 to 2020. The agricultural gross domestic product (AGDP), which is a measure of the amount of food that is produced by agriculture, poverty rate, the unemployment rate, the crime rate, and the amount of money spent by the federal government on internal security in Nigeria are the factors that are considered to be explanatory (independent). The findings indicate that while there is a positive association between agricultural production and both the agricultural sector loan

guarantee programme fund and the government's recurrent spending on the agriculture sector, the relationship is not substantial. This is one of the conclusions that can be drawn from the findings. The findings also indicate that there is a positive association between commercial bank credits and agricultural production, but this relationship is not statistically significant. Additionally, there is a negative relationship between interest rate and agricultural output, although this relationship is statistically significant.

Using secondary time series data spanning the years 1960-2017, Enimu et al. (2019) conducted a research on the influence that insurgency has had on development in Nigeria. The findings indicated that the quantity of food production and the amount of money spent by the government on agriculture had a direct impact on the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). On the other hand, insurgencies such as Boko Haram, the Niger Delta, herders and farmers, and ethno-religious crises have a negative impact on GDP. Additionally, Eneji et al. (2019) investigated the impact that insecurity has on the level of agricultural output in Nigeria using Agricultural Gross Domestic Product (AGDP), poverty (POV), unemployment (UNMP), and crime rate (CR), as well as the federal government's recurrent spending on internal security (FREXIS). On the basis of the findings, it was discovered that CR and UNMP had a negative relationship with agricultural production (AGDP).

Primus (2019) conducted research that looked into the impact that commercial banks had on the growth of the real estate market in Nigeria during a period of 37 years, from 1981 to 2017. Interest rate information on commercial bank loan extended to the agricultural industry with data. The findings indicated that there is a connection between the provision of bank loans and the continued growth of agricultural production in Nigeria over the long term. The ECM was determined to be negative and statistically significant at a level of significance of 5%, according to the findings of the research. Agricultural development in Nigeria was shown to be adversely associated to interest rates, while the research revealed that commercial banks' loan to agriculture and agricultural credit guarantee plan are favourably related to agricultural development. The study also indicated that agricultural development is positively related to agricultural development. Similarly, Enilolobo and Ode-Omenka (2018) investigated the influence that loans had on the agricultural production in Nigeria from 1978 to 2016. Based on the results of the research, it was discovered that there is no long-term correlation between the amount of deposit money bank credit extended to the agricultural sector in Nigeria and the production of the agricultural sector. The results of the research are further in accordance with a priori assumptions, as the findings indicate that the provision of deposit money bank credit to the farm sector in Nigeria has a favourable and substantial influence on the production of the agriculture sector in Nigeria.

In a similar vein, Ogbuabor and Nwosu (2017) investigated the influence that agricultural loan from deposit money banks had on agricultural production in Nigeria. They did this by using an error correction model and yearly time series data for the years 1981-2014. The findings suggest that there is a connection between the variables that is described as being in balance. In addition, the study discover that the agricultural loan provided by deposit money banks has a favourable and large influence on agricultural production over the long term, but that this impact is fairly little over the short term. Additionally, the study discover that agricultural land and labour force have a negative influence on agricultural production, and this is true both in the long-term and in the short-term. On the other hand, the influence of climate change factors, including yearly rainfall and average temperature, remained insignificant throughout the whole

process.

In a similar vein, Asom and Ijirshar (2016) investigated the influence that loans from deposit money banks (DMBs) has on the overall performance of the agricultural sector. According to the findings of the research, the provision of credit by deposit money banks has a favourable and considerable influence on the expansion of agricultural production over the long term. The loan rate, on the other hand, had a detrimental effect on the agricultural production of the nation. In each year, the system returns to long-run equilibrium at a rate of 19.5%, as shown by the results of the error correction model. This indicates that the system corrects its original disequilibrium. In conclusion, Anthony et al. (2015) study the impact that loans from deposit money banks had on the expansion of the agricultural industry in Nigeria between the years 1988 and 2011. For the purpose of the study, an ex-post facto research design was used. Both the loans provided by deposit money banks and the fund established by the agricultural credit guarantee scheme were shown to have a positive correlation with the production of the agricultural sector. On the other hand, it was found that the link between the agricultural loan guarantee programme fund and the fund was minimal.

At the same time, this research conducted an analysis of previous empirical investigations and observed some findings that were conflicting and lacked definitive evidence. For example, previous research on the relationship between bank operations and agricultural sector productivity by Omolola et al. (2023), Nwafor (2022), Onwuka (2021), Nura (2020), Irene et al. (2020), Sylvester (2020), Akinuli and Osagiede (2023), Enilolobo and Ode-Omenka (2018), Ogbuabor and Nwosu (2017), Asom and Ijirshar (2016), and Anthony et al. (2015) fall this category. These studies found that bank operations have a significant and positive contribution to agricultural sector productivity. In contrast, Mbotto et al. (2022) argue in their research that bank operations, particularly lending rates, have a negative impact on the productivity of the agricultural sector. On the other hand, Onuegbu et al. (2022) and Ilesanmi and Odefadehan (2022) found that bank operations do not have any impact whatsoever on the productivity of the agricultural sector.

In a similar vein, Ijeomah and Wonah (2022), Eneji et al (2019), and Enimu et al (2019) all concurred that insecurity had a significant impact on the productivity of the agricultural sector. However, they only took into account insurgencies like Boko-haram, Herders/farmer, and ethno-religious crises. Furthermore, they acknowledged the implications of kidnapping and armed robbery on farmers, as well as the long-term impact on output. The article also found that prior studies either analyzed individual indicators such as bank credit, lending rate, or insecurity on agricultural sector productivity. However, none of the studies have comprehensively evaluated the influence of bank operation and insecurity on agricultural sector productivity. This was observed by the paper which constitutes a research gap.

3. Methodology

This research is based on secondary data that was collected from the World Bank's World Development Indicators, the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), and audited annual reports and accounts of deposit money institutions (DBMs) during the period of time spanning from 1985 to 2021. The Lending Rate (LR), the Deposit Rate (DR), the Kidnapping Rate (KPR), and the Armed Robbery Rate (ARR) were used as proxies for "bank operation and insecurity." On the other hand, the agricultural contribution to gross domestic product (AGDP) was chosen as a means of capturing "Agricultural Sector

Productivity.” The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was used to do the unit root test on the variables, while the Auto-regressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) Model was used in the study.

3.1 Model Specification

This study is based on the modification of Eneji, et al (2019), and Anthony et al (2015).

Eneji, et al (2019) investigated the effects of insecurity on agricultural productivity in Nigeria by specifying a functional model as follows:

$$AGDP = f(POV, UNMP, CR, FGREXIS) \quad (1)$$

Similarly, Anthony et al (2015) investigated the role of deposit money banks credit on the growth of the agricultural sector in Nigeria by specifying the following functional model:

$$TOAS = f(DMBL, DMBLR, ACGSF) \quad (2)$$

Where: POV= Poverty, TOAS= Total Output of agricultural Sector, UNMP = Unemployment rate, CR= Crime Rate, and FGREXIS = Federal government recurrent expenditure on internal security, DMBL = Deposit Money Banks Loans to Agricultural Sector, DMBLR = Deposit Money Banks' Lending Rate and ACGSF = Agricultural Sector Guarantee Scheme Fund.

Equation (1) and (2) was modified by introducing deposit rate (DR), kidnapping rate (KPR), and armed robbery rate (ARR), as new variables. The functional form of the model is specified as follows:

$$AGDP = f(LR, DR, KPR, ARR) \quad (3)$$

The mathematical model could be symbolically expressed as;

$$AGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LR + \beta_2 DR + \beta_3 KPR + \beta_4 ARR \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) above is transformed into an econometric model by incorporating the disturbance term (ϵ) as follows:

$$AGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LR + \beta_2 DR + \beta_3 KPR + \beta_4 ARR + \epsilon \quad (5)$$

It is also possible to turn a highly skewed variable into one that is more nearly normal by using logarithmic transformation, which is a handy method (Kenneth 2011).

For the purpose of this investigation, the model that has been updated and accepted currently takes the form of

$$LAGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LR + \beta_2 DR + \beta_3 LKPR + \beta_4 LARR + \epsilon \quad (6)$$

Where:

LAGDP = Log of Agricultural Sector contribution to Gross domestic Product, LR = Lending Rate, DR = Deposit Rate, LKPR = Log of Kidnapping Rate, LARR = Log of Armed Robbery Rate, f = functional relationship β_0 = Intercept of relationship in the model/constant β_1 - β_4 = Coefficients of each independent or explanatory variable ϵ = Stochastic or Error term.

The ARDL Methodology

The study employed the autoregressive distributive lag model (ARDL) proposed by Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001) to estimate the relationship between the variables. The model is therefore specified in unrestricted error correction form to test for cointegration relationship as follows:

$$\Delta LAGDP_t = \beta_0 + \Delta LAGDP_{t-1} + \sum \beta_{1,t} \Delta LR_{t-1} + \sum \beta_{2,t} \Delta DR_{t-1} + \sum \beta_{3,t} \Delta LKPR_{t-1} + \sum \beta_{4,t} \Delta LARR_{t-1} + \Delta LAGDP_{t-1} + \sum \Phi_{1,t} \Delta LR_{t-1} + \sum \Phi_{2,t} \Delta DR_{t-1} + \sum \Phi_{3,t} \Delta LKPR_{t-1} + \sum \Phi_{4,t} \Delta LARR_{t-1} + U_t \dots \dots \quad (7)$$

The inference here is that, if the computed F-statistics is greater than the upper bound critical value at 5%, there is evidence of cointegration. If the computed F-statistics is less than the lower

bound critical value at 5% there is no cointegration. However, if the value of the computed F-statistics lies between the upper and the lower critical values, then the inference is said to be inconclusive. Once cointegration relationship exists, the long-run model would be estimated as specified:

$$LAGDP_{t-1} = \sum \Phi_1 tLR_{t-1} + \sum \Phi_2 tDR_{t-1} + \sum \Phi_3 tLKPR + \sum \Phi_4 tLARR_{t-1} + U_t \tag{8}$$

Similarly, the short-run model of the error correction specification would be estimated to ascertain the short-run dynamic behaviour of the variables in the model as;

$$\Delta LAGDP_t = \beta_0 + \Delta LAGDP_{t-1} + \sum \beta_1 t\Delta LR_{t-1} + \sum \beta_2 t\Delta DR_{t-1} + \sum \beta_3 t\Delta LKPR_{t-1} + \sum \beta_4 t\Delta LARR_{t-1} + ECT_{t-1} + U_t \tag{9}$$

Where the ECT in the above equation is specified as;

$$ECT_t = \Delta LAGDP_{t-1} - \beta_0 - \Delta LAGDP_{t-1} - \sum \beta_1 t\Delta LR_{t-1} - \sum \beta_2 t\Delta DR_{t-1} - \sum \beta_3 t\Delta LKPR_{t-1} - \sum \beta_4 t\Delta LARR_{t-1} \tag{10}$$

Finally, the study diagnosed the model by conducting test for serial correlation, Ramsey reset test and heteroskedasticity.

Description of Variables in the Model

Agricultural Sector Contribution to GDP (AGDP): This refers to the percentage or proportion of a country’s gross domestic product (GDP) that is generated by the agricultural activities within that country. Agricultural sector contribution to gross domestic product is used to proxy the dependent variable “Agricultural Sector Productivity”, and would be measured in billions of Naira.

Lending Rate (LR): This is percentage charged by a financial institution for lending money. Lending rate is used in this paper to capture the independent variable “bank operations”. It is hypothesized that increase in lending rate, will result to a decline in agricultural sector productivity. Thus, an inverse relationship is expected between lending rate and agricultural sector productivity. Lending rate is measured in percentage (%).

Deposit Rate (DR): This refers to the interest rate that a financial institution pay to individuals for depositing funds in a savings account. Deposit rate is used in this paper to proxy the independent variable “bank operations”. This research believed that increase in deposit rate will increase banks liquidity thereby making it possible for investors to access more loans. Hence a positive relationship is expected between deposit rate and agricultural sector productivity. This study would measure deposit rate in percentage (%).

Kidnaping Rate (KPR): This refers to the frequency or incidence of kidnapping within a specific population or geographical area over a given period. Kidnaping rate is used in this paper to proxy the independent variable “insecurity”. It is assumed in this study that increase in kidnapping will create an atmosphere of insecurity, deterring, both domestic (farmers) and foreign investors. Therefore an inverse relationship is expected between kidnapping and

agricultural sector productivity.

Armed Robbery Rate (ARR): This denotes the frequency or incidence of armed robbery within a specific population or geographical area over a given period. It is a statistical measure that quantifies the number of armed robbery incidents relative to a standard unit, and measured as a rate per 100,000. Armed robbery rate is used in this paper to proxy the independent variable “insecurity”. It is assumed in this study that increase in armed robbery rate create an atmosphere of insecurity, deterring, both domestic (farmers) and foreign investors. Therefore, an inverse relationship is expected between kidnapping and agricultural sector productivity.

4. EMPIRICAL DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Unit Root Test

A unit root test known as the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test was used in the research project to determine the order of integration of the variables that were being investigated. This was done in order to pick the proper approach and prevent false regression.

Table 1: Unit Root Test Using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF)

Variables	Levels				Order of Integration	P-value
	T. Statistics	5% Critical Value	T. Statistics	5% Critical Value		
LAGDP	-2.764461	-2.945842	-3.838641	-2.948404	I(0)	0.0059
LR	-3.834937	-2.945842			I(0)	0.0059
DR	-0.852240	-2.945842	-6.013315	-2.948404	I(1)	0.0000
LKPR	-0.447542	-2.945842	-6.179420	-2.948404	I(1)	0.0000
LARR	-1.362058	-2.945842	-4.544853	-2.948404	I(1)	0.0009

Level of significance at 5%

In accordance with the findings shown in Table 1, the variables that were a part of the research were subjected to Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) tests in order to determine whether or not they could be classified as stationary series or non-stationary series. According to the findings of the stationarity test, LAGDP, DR, LKPR, and LARR were determined to be stationary at the first difference I(1). However, LR was found to be stationary at the level I(0). The stationarity of the variables is evaluated, and it is determined that the variables display mixed order of integration or stationarity at level and first difference. The Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) approach was used for the purpose of conducting the analysis of the data. This method is capable of controlling both stationarity at level I(0) and first difference I(1). Consequently, the ARDL test is the most suitable method of analysis since it takes into consideration both short-term and long-term trends when analyzing the relationship between the variables that are dependent and those that are independent.

Table 2: ARDL Bound Test

Test Statistics	Value	K
F-statistics	5.752897	4
Significance	I (0)	I(1)
10%	2.45	3.52
5%	2.86	4.01
2.5%	3.25	4.49
1%	3.74	5.06

An examination of the F-statistics in relation to the critical bound values is shown in Table 2, which contains the findings of the bound test. The value of the F-statistic is 5.752897. At a significance level of 0.05, the result indicated that the F-statistic is more than both the lower and upper bounds of the critical values, which are 2.86 and 4.01, respectively. This implies that the F-statistic was statistically significant. As a consequence of this, there is a degree of co-integration between the functioning of banks, the level of insecurity, and the level of production in the agricultural sector in Nigeria.

Table 3: ARDL Long-run Result (Dependent Variable = LAGDP)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistics	Prob
LR	0.653248	0.276427	2.363183	0.0212
DR	0.161991	1.237197	0.130934	0.8975
LKPR	0.362015	0.114413	-3.164107	0.0017
LARR	0.458607	5.323813	-0.086143	0.9324

$$EC = LAGDP - (0.6532*LR + 0.1620*DR - 0.3620*LKPR - 0.4586*LARR)$$

A positive relationship of +0.653248 is suggested to exist between the lending rate (LR) and the log value of agriculture sector contribution to gross domestic product (LAGDP) as a proxy for agricultural sector productivity. According to Table 3 indicates that there is a correlation between LR and LAGDP. This means that one percentage point of LR will result to annual LAGDP of 0.66 percent. The p-value of 0.0212 indicates that there is a statistically significant relationship between LR and LAGDP, which is an exciting finding but disagrees with earlier study conducted Mboto et al (2022). The findings of the coefficient of deposit rate (DR) (0.161991) suggest that there is a positive relationship between DR and LAGDP. This implies that a percentage point increase in DR will lead to an increase of LAGDP of around 0.16 percent (%) each year. The p-value of 0.8975, on the other hand, indicates that there is no statistically significant relationship between DR and LAGDP. However, prior study by Osagiede (2023), disagrees with this study and infer that bank activities had significant influence on agricultural sector productivity.

The estimated coefficient of LKPR indicate that there is a positive relationship of 0.362015 with LAGDP. It may be deduced from this that a percentage increase in LKPR would lead to a rise of around 0.36 percent in LAGDP. There is a statistically significant relationship between LKPR and LAGDP, as shown by the p-value of 0.0017, which indicates that the relationship is negative. Though, previous study conducted by Ijeomah and Wonah (2022), disagree with this findings and submit that increase in prices of food stuff is as a result of frequent attack by herdsmen.

The estimated coefficient of LARR shows a positive relationship of 0.458607 with LAGDP. The result signifies that a unit rise in LARR is related to a rise in annual LAGDP of about 0.46 percent. Remarkably, the p-value of 0.9324 shows that there is no statistical significant relationship between LARR and LAGDP. However, previous study conducted by Ijeomah and Wonah (2022), agree with this finding and submit that increase in prices of food stuff is as a result of frequent attack by headsmen.

Table 4: ARDL Short-run Result (Dependent Variable = LAGDP)

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob
C	0.413747	0.052132	7.936504	0.0000
D(LR)	-0.003212	0.007993	-0.401882	0.6931
D(LR(-1))	-0.027180	0.010437	-2.604157	0.0192
D(LR(-2))	-0.028618	0.007942	-3.603579	0.0024
D(DR)	0.009441	0.017246	0.547423	0.5916
D(DR(-1))	0.028359	0.016306	1.739143	0.1012
D(DR(-2))	0.015965	0.013594	1.174384	0.2574
D(LKPR)	0.030035	0.054470	0.551400	0.5890
D(LKPR(-1))	0.132231	0.053125	2.490941	0.0428
D(LKPR(-2))	0.009413	0.057185	0.164608	0.8713
D(LARR)	0.217743	0.130812	1.664545	0.1155
D(LARR(-1))	0.190249	0.143241	1.328176	0.2028
D(LARR(-2))	-0.083444	0.142795	-0.584362	0.5671
ECM(-1)	-0.027866	0.005754	-4.843099	0.0002
Adj R²=0.466700, F-statistics = 3.221453 (0.009296), DW =1.608812				

Based on the outcome of the ARDL model as shown in Table 4, it is evident that the coefficient of the error correction component is both significant and negative. In other words, the relevance of the negative sign is justified by its presence. Therefore, it can be said that the ECM will be successful in resolving any deviations from the equilibrium that exists over the long term. The fact that the coefficient of the ECM is -0.027866 suggests that the rate of adjustment to long run equilibrium is 0.03% when any departure from the past is rectified in the current period implies that the speed of adjustment is 0.03%. As a result, the current value of AGDP undergoes a gradual adjustment in response to variations in LR, DR, LKPR, and LARR.

As a consequence of the findings of the ARDL short-run, it is clear that the value of the constant parameter (B_0) is positive, namely at 0.413747. It can be deduced from this that the annual growth rate of the AGDP will increase by 0.41 percent when all the independent variables are equal to zero. When it comes to the coefficient of lending rate (LR), the coefficients are -0.027180 and -0.028618 respectively. The conclusion that can be drawn from this is that LR has a negative relationship with AGDP in both the first and second years. The results are consistent with the apriori. The negative conclusion indicates that a one-unit increase in the loan rate would ultimately lead to a 0.03 percent decline in LAGDP. In a fascinating turn of events, the p-value reveals that there is a statistically significant connection between LR and AGDP. Past study conducted Mboto et al (2022) agrees with this finding.

The estimated coefficients of DR is positive, with values of 0.009441, 0.028359, and 0.015965 respectively, for the current year, at lag one and lag two. This result indicates that a priori is correct. The positive finding indicates that an increase of one unit in the deposit rate will result in a rise of 0.02 percent in the aggregate gross domestic product. Despite this, the p-value shows that there is no statistically significant relationship between DR and AGDP. However, prior study by Osagiede (2023), disagrees with this study and infer that bank activities had significant influence on agricultural sector productivity. In addition, the log value of the kidnapping rate (LKPR) is both positive and statistically significant in the preceding year period, coming in at 0.132231 for the LKPR. In light of this, it may be concluded that there is a positive relationship between LKPR and AGDP. The log value of the arm robbery rate (LARR) in at lag two is negative (-0.083444). In light of this, it may be deduced that there is a negative link between LARR and AGDP.

Further results with regard to adjusted R-Square (R²) validated the strength of the link by recording 47% variation in dependent variable. Given that the model has a comparable probability value of 0.009296 shows that the model as a whole is statistically significant. A Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.608812 shows that the series are not auto-correlated. All of the findings pointed to the fact that the business operations of banks and the level of security in Nigeria had a substantial influence on the level of production in the agricultural sector.

Diagnostic Test

Table 5: Ramsey Reset Test, Serial Correlation LM Test and Homoscedasticity Test

	Results	
	F-Statistic	Prob.Value
Ramsey Reset Test	3.865382	0.0681
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	0.533887	0.5987
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test	2.832999	0.0715

As shown in Table 5, the results of the diagnostic test suggest that the Ramsey reset linearity test showed f-statistic of (3.865382) with a calculated p-value of 0.0681, which is larger than the crucial value of 0.05. This shows that the model is properly described. This is the case since the p-value is greater than the critical value of 0.05.

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test result shows that the F-statistic is 0.533887, and the Chi-Square probability value is 0.5987. These numerical values are not statistically significant. As a consequence of this, the null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be rejected. The results of the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test for heteroscedasticity show that the F-statistic is 2.832999, and the Chi-Square probability value is 0.0715. These values are not statistically significant. Due to the fact that the value of the probability Chi-square is more than 5% ($P > 0.05$), the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity cannot be rejected.

Stability Test

Cusum

Figure 1, shows summary of the stability (Cusum) of the model. The graph showed that the model is stable, this is evident to the fact that, the blue line inside the graph is in between the two red lines. This also indicates that it is less than 0.05 level of significance.

From the figure above, the dotted red lines also represented the critical bounds. The figure also shows that the sum of squares of the recursive residuals of the AGDP is relatively stable especially for the period of bank operation and agricultural sector productivity. Most especially for the period under investigation AGDP has remained within the critical bounds. The results imply that the null hypothesis of no stability of the short-run AGDP can be rejected at 5% significance level.

Policy Implication

- i. Investors don't worry about lending rate, they seem to be more concerned about availability of fund than cost of borrowing.
- ii. Kidnaping, Armed robbery and other forms of insecurity has not significantly affected agriculture but measures needs to be taken before it gets out of hand. Security forces need to re strategies to cope with the menace.
- iii. More attractive deposit regime is desirable to encourage the agricultural sector to patronize the banks.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The auto-regressive distributive lag (ARDL) was used in this research to investigate the influence that bank operations and insecurity have on the level of production in the agriculture sector in Nigeria. We utilized the lending rate (LR), the deposit rate (DR), the kidnapping rate (KPR), and the armed robbery rate (ARR) to capture the independent variables, and we used the contribution of the agricultural sector to gross domestic product (AGDP) as a proxy for the dependent variable over a period of 36 years, from 1985 to 2021. As a result of the data, it is possible to draw the conclusion that the productivity of the agricultural sector was significantly impacted by both the operation of banks and the presence of insecurity. To be more specific,

the loan rate had a negative impact on the production of the agricultural sector in the previous year, which was a short-term effect. On the other hand, the kidnapping rate indicated a negative but substantial link with agricultural sector productivity in the long-term. It should be noted, however, that the rate of deposits and the rate of armed robbery are not strongly connected to the production of the agricultural sector. As a result, the conclusion that was reached was that the stability of the financial system had a major effect on the agricultural productivity growth rate in Nigeria

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendation were made below;

- i. Authorities should immediately reduce the rising lending rate as a target variable to control inflation, expand farmer's access to credit which will enhance productivity and job creation.
- ii. Central Bank through the deposit money banks should increase the deposit rate. this will encourage depositors to save more thereby increasing their liquidity position and the same time enhance agricultural sector productivity via mobilization and creating access for credit to investors in the sector.
- iii. The federal government should strengthen their security institutions (Police, Army, Navy etc.) to tackle crime. This will boost both individual, investors 'particularly the farmer confidence which will in turn enable them continue with their daily farming activity.

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